

A Study of Hysterectomy in Women Aged 40 years and Less for Benign Conditions

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Abstract : In England 12.7% of benign hysterectomies are performed on women under 40 years old.

Different routes of hysterectomy

- Abdominal hysterectomy (AH)
- Vaginal hysterectomy
- Laparoscopic hysterectomy that include total laparoscopic hysterectomy and laparoscopic assisted vaginal hysterectomy
- Subtotal hysterectomy

Aims and objectives

Comparison of national hysterectomy rate to hysterectomy in UHB trust

- Identify indications of hysterectomy.
- Histology
- Compliance for conservative management prior to hysterectomy as per NICE guidelines.

Methodology

- Retrospective data collection from concerto and clinical portal from January 2019 to December 2022.
- Hysterectomies done for women aged 40 yrs and less at UHB for benign conditions.
- Women with abnormal endometrial and cervical biopsy excluded.

Figure 1; Age Group

Ages :26 to 40 yrs, Mean Age :35 yrs

Figure 2: Ethnicity

Figure 3: Parity

Figure 4: Symptoms at presentation

Figure 5: Treatment offered before hysterectomy

Figure 6: Indications at surgery

Figure 7: Histology

Conclusion

- The hysterectomy rate for benign disease of women aged less than equal to 40 at UHB is slightly lower than national rate 12.76% of 10.5%.
- The most common symptoms with which women presented is heavy menstrual bleeding and pain or both together.
- Its worth noting that most women were parous , and first line of management for HMB was done.

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- All women have tried alternate treatment either conservative like medications, hormonal before hysterectomy was offered.
 - Abnormal uterine bleeding and Endometriosis were the most common diagnosis.
 - Histology report showed 98% women had hysterectomy for benign condition and it was unremarkable, 2% had CIN II.

Action plan

- 100 % compliance is seen in women according to NICE guideline first line of management .
- Reaudit in 2024 to see for incidence of hysterectomy

Medtronic